

EFFECTS OF PROCESS CONDITIONS ON AEROSPACE GRADE EPOXY/CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

M.J. Jennings, T., Banicevich, A. Grobler, and S. Al-Assafi

Introduction

- Aerospace composite production demands are still increasing
- Alternative processing methods can help to increase rate
- New processing methods require comprehensive validation and qualification
- This study shows some initial promising results when curing composites using isostatic heat transfer fluid
- Initial process quality metrics used were:

- Interlaminar Shear Strength
- Void Content
- Surface Porosity

Methodology

Material: Hexcel® HexPly® F584™ prepreg
 Layup:[0]₈T, compaction after ply 1 and 4.

Experiment #	Cure process	Pressure applied	Heating rate	Dwell Temperature	Dwell Time
1	Autoclave	80 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
2	Autoclave	250 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
3	Autoclave	620 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
4	Cure	80 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
5	Cure	250 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	60 minutes
6	Cure	250 kPa	5°C/min	177°C	60 minutes

Results

Cure process	Pressure applied	Heating rate	Void Content
Autoclave	80 kPa	2°C/min	1.06%
	250 kPa		0.01%
	620 kPa		0.00%
Cure	80 kPa	2°C/min	0.31%
	250 kPa		0.08%
	250 kPa	5°C/min	0.00%

Surface Porosity

Cure process	80 kPa 2°C/min	250 kPa 2°C/min	620 kPa 2°C/min
Autoclave	15.02%	0.003%	0.00%
Cure process	80 kPa 2°C/min	250 kPa 2°C/min	250 kPa 5°C/min
Cure	3.44%	0.10%	0.04%

Conclusions

Interlaminar Shear Strength

- No detrimental effect compared to autoclave when curing at lower pressure or faster heating when using isostatic processing

Internal porosity

- Isostatic processing at 2.5 bar resulted in similar porosity to 2.5 and 6.2 bar Autoclave specimens
- A faster heating rate resulted in less voids

Surface porosity

- Isostatic processing at 2.5 bar resulted in similar porosity to 2.5 and 6.2 bar Autoclave specimens
- A faster heating rate resulted in less surface porosity

Future work:

- Thicker laminates
- Faster heating rates
- Modelling of kinetics and rheology
- Initiate aerospace qualification testing program